

ANALYSIS OF MODERN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON TOLERANCE

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Abstract

This article discusses the important aspects of the problem of tolerance, the features of its emergence and formation. Also, the analysis of various research works devoted to the problem of tolerance is presented.

Key words: religion, tolerance, religious tolerance, psychological character, trust, approach

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются важные аспекты проблемы толерантности, особенности ее возникновения и формирования. Также представлен анализ различных научных работ, посвященных проблеме толерантности.

Ключевые слова: религия, толерантность, религиозная толерантность, психологический характер, доверие, подход.

According to E.V.Magomedova, tolerance can be considered on the basis of two levels of human consciousness: rational-logical and emotional-emotional. To be patient with another person, to understand him, requires not only the knowledge of such behavior, but also the feeling of this behavior. From this point of view, tolerance is always a personal-emotional behavior. Such a mental state of a person V.S. Solovev calls spirituality. Such an assumption is emphasized by the conclusion that tolerance is closely related to morality on an emotional-emotional level. In addition, tolerance is not considered historical at the emotional-emotional level, because it is entrenched in the cultural-historical traditions of many nations.

True tolerance is provided by the inner spiritual freedom of a person, and it is not always compatible with outer freedom[3].

The phenomenon of tolerance was described by P.F. Komogorov analyzes from three different positions. Firstly, in the context of the anthropological problem in the form of "I and You", secondly, the problems of values from an axiological point of view, and thirdly, in terms of praxeology, including communication activities. Originally, the topic "I and You" was written by the German thinker L. It was developed by Feuerbach. "He asserts that he is a separate person, he is somehow isolated and does not reflect the essence of humanity, morality and thinking. The human essence is manifested only in communication, in the unity of man with man, and only in relying on the reality of the difference "I and You". In this L. Feuerbach believes that the human essence is not given to a person by birth from nature, but is recognized from the position of naturalism. M. Buber, L. Unlike Feuerbach, he assigns a sacral (holy) character to the relationship between "I and You". In his opinion, tolerance is related to the way people live in small communities and groups where they communicate with each other.

From this point of view, a tolerant person gains his uniqueness by realizing the relationship of "I and You", that is, by interacting with other people, of course. An intolerant person isolates himself from others[3].

According to the scientific basis, the problem of "I and You" was analyzed in a different direction in Russian religious philosophy of the 20th century. N.A. Berdyaev emphasizes the existence of "We" in addition to "I and You", "He". But "We" has a two-sided nature. First, "We" is the quality given to any "I" from the outside as a social community, and secondly, "We" is the communication between the internal social community and "I". "We" is the primary social unit, "I" is determined as the content and quality of life, and it determines the attitude not only to "You", but also to the human plurality.

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This "We" is N.A. Berdyaev calls the world of objectivity, communication, and it embodies peace, friendship, love, consensus and compromise. The individual always tries to get rid of his loneliness. S.L. According to Frank, "We" is manifested in the activities of the sense of the Motherland, religious unity, family, army, church, economic enterprises, and spiritual cooperation that covers people. In his opinion, the relationship between "I" and "You" is contradictory. In this relationship there is also a negative state, which is manifested in the conclusion that the other person is interfering in my life, and this situation creates a threat to my personality. There is also a positive case. Because "I" can find the spirit of brotherhood in "You", and in this I will be free from the scourge of loneliness. The deep essence of the relationship between "I" and "You" is revealed with the help of a universal phenomenon - love, which directs all life activities of a person to control the love of parents to children, teachers to students, believers to God. This love is manifested in caring for others, respect, sympathy, etc[4].

In the form of "I" and "You" relationship, "You" is recognized as a threat to the identity of "I", and this situation can be the reason for the emergence of intolerance. The similarity and closeness in the relationship between "I" and "You" creates conditions for the formation and emergence of tolerance.

Psychologists emphasize the values-based nature of tolerance and connect it with the development of human morality. Such an approach was adopted by S.M.

We can see in the works of Shalyutin. It explores tolerance as a universal human value passed down through the ages. In Behaviorism, tolerance is seen primarily as a special human trait. Also, in the cognitive approach, tolerance is based on knowledge and rational arguments. From the existential-humanitarian point of view, full and thorough tolerance is a directly realized, proud and responsible social phenomenon. S.L. According to Bratchenko, such tolerance does not lead to automatism and simple patterns of actions, it is a value and a vital position, the implementation of which in a concrete situation acquires a certain meaning, and the subject of tolerance is required to search for this meaning and a responsible decision.

Such an approach, A.G. From Asmolov's point of view, tolerance is not a solid rule or a ready-made recipe for consumption, especially a mandatory requirement for punishment, on the contrary, it should serve as a responsible choice of a person - an approach to life based on a valuable tolerance.

Foreign and domestic work on tolerance shows that it is difficult to give a general definition of tolerance. Therefore, a diversification approach is being followed in this matter. While discussing this approach, I. Pettai talks about the specific development dynamics of tolerance and tries to distinguish several periods of tolerance formation. Therefore, it is not correct to say that a higher level of tolerance is always preferable[1].

Also, this author proposes to separate another conditional "tolerance component" - verbal. If the cognitive component refers to the precise measurement of perception, understanding, thinking, interpretation in the direction of the implementation of the principles of tolerance, the verbal component is limited to the organization of knowledge.

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